

Physical Models for 2.4 mm and 3.5 mm Coaxial VNA Calibration Kits Developed within the NIST Microwave Uncertainty Framework

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Abstract — We developed physical models of commercially-available 2.4 mm and 3.5 mm coaxial calibration kits for vector network analyzers. These models support multiline thru-reflect-line (TRL) and open-short-load-thru (OSLT) calibrations, and include error mechanisms in each of the standards' constituent parameters that can be utilized in the NIST Microwave Uncertainty Framework to propagate uncertainties. For both connector sizes, we calibrated a network analyzer using the two calibration methods, and compared measurements and uncertainties made on a number of verification devices. In both cases, we showed that the two calibrations agree to within their respective uncertainties.

Index Terms — calibration, coaxial, physical models, uncertainty, vector network analyzer, verification.

I. INTRODUCTION

The multiline, thru-reflect-line (TRL) calibration [1] is perhaps the most fundamental and accurate vector network analyzer (VNA) calibration for coaxial circuits. Multiline TRL calibrations measure the propagation constant of the line standards so that the characteristic impedance can be transformed to a selected reference impedance, and offer high bandwidth and accuracy through the use of multiple transmission line standards. However, a set of coaxial lines, some relatively long, is required to obtain a wide-band measurement. Coaxial airlines also require considerable care to ensure good connections without damaging the standards. Furthermore, a set of lines can be costly, and measurements are time-consuming.

Other types of VNA calibrations make use of compact, lumped-element standards; the most common being open-short-load-thru (OSLT) and line-reflect-match (LRM) methods [2]. They provide calibration procedures that are easier to perform, oftentimes at the cost of lower accuracy.

In this paper, we utilize the NIST Microwave Uncertainty Framework [3-6] to develop physical models of commercially available 2.4 mm and 3.5 mm multiline TRL and OSLT coaxial calibrations kits. The NIST Microwave Uncertainty Framework utilizes parallel sensitivity and Monte-Carlo analyses, and enables us to capture and propagate the significant S-parameter measurement uncertainties and statistical correlations between them [7]. By identifying and modeling the physical error mechanisms in the calibration standards, we can determine the statistical correlations between both the scattering parameters at a single frequency

and uncertainties at different frequencies. These uncertainties can then be propagated to the measurements of the devices under test. In the following sections, we describe our methodology in further detail, and compare measurements and uncertainties made on a number of verification devices.

I. 3.5 MM COAXIAL CALIBRATIONS

For the 3.5 mm coaxial devices, we began by modeling the multiline TRL calibration standards (a thru connection, an offset short, and six airlines of varying lengths) for purposes of determining uncertainties. Table I lists the line lengths and associated uncertainties for the multiline TRL standards, and Table II lists the other sources of uncertainty for the standards. Our values and distributions of the uncertainties come from a variety of sources, including manufacturers' specifications and an IEEE standard [8].

The NIST Microwave Uncertainty Framework was employed to construct models for the calibration standards. The airline and offset-short standards were modeled with closed-form expressions for coaxial lines of finite metal conductivity [9]. The framework was also used for automatically propagating the uncertainties to the calibrated verification devices in conjunction with the calibration engine, StatisticCAL™ [10, 11], which utilizes a "mix-and-match" philosophy to VNA calibrations.

Next, the OSLT standards were modeled with the values and uncertainties listed in Tables II and III. We compared our physical models of the open and short to the polynomial models specified by the manufacturer [12], as shown in Figures 1-4. Figures 1 and 3 plot the magnitudes of the reflection coefficients as a function of frequency, while Figures 2 and 4 plot the differences in phase with respect to those of the physical models. Additionally, we compared our physical models to measurements of the standards using the multiline TRL calibration, the results of which are also displayed in Figures 1-4. We see that our physical models closely match the polynomial models, and the uncertainty bounds of our physical models, depicted by the dotted curves, span the majority of the measured values. We modeled the load standard as a simple 50 Ohm resistor after observing that the magnitudes of the measured reflection coefficients for both the male and female connectors were less than -40 dB at most frequencies, as displayed in Figure 5.

Table I. Lengths and uncertainties of the 3.5 mm TRL standards.

Line Designation	Length (mm) \pm Uncertainty (Distribution)
Thru	0.000 \pm 0.009 (Rectangular)
AL3527	16.154 \pm 0.009 (Rectangular)
AL3530	37.504 \pm 0.009 (Rectangular)
MMC225	22.500 \pm 0.009 (Rectangular)
MMC244	24.400 \pm 0.009 (Rectangular)
MMC250	25.000 \pm 0.009 (Rectangular)
MMC300	30.000 \pm 0.009 (Rectangular)
Offset Shorts	9.520 \pm 0.009 (Rectangular)

Table II. Physical error mechanisms of the 3.5 mm standards.

Mechanism (units)	Value \pm Uncertainty (Distribution)
Inner Cond. Diameter (mm)	1.5199 \pm 0.002 (Rectangular)
Outer Cond. Diameter (mm)	3.5 \pm 0.002 (Rectangular)
Pin Diameter (mm)	0.927 \pm 0.008 (Rectangular)
Pin Depth (mm)	0.0153 \pm 0.0153 (Rectangular)
Metal Conductivity (S/m)	7.9 $\times 10^6 \pm 4 \times 10^6$ (Rectangular)
Relative Dielectric Constant	1 \pm 0
Dielectric Loss Tangent	0 \pm 0

Table III. Physical error mechanisms of the 3.5 mm OSLT standards.

Mechanism (units)	Value \pm Uncertainty (Distribution)
Open Offset Length (mm)	9.51 \pm 0.05 (Rectangular)
Open Metal Conductivity (S/m)	5 $\times 10^6 \pm 4 \times 10^6$ (Rectangular)
Open Conductance (1/ Ω)	0 \pm 0
Open Capacitance (pF)	0 \pm 0
Short Offset Length (mm)	9.52 \pm 0.05 (Rectangular)
Short Metal Conductivity (S/m)	6 $\times 10^6 \pm 5 \times 10^6$ (Rectangular)
Short Resistance (Ω)	0 \pm 0
Short Inductance (nH)	0 \pm 0
Load Resistance (Ω)	50.0 \pm 0.1
Load Inductance (nH)	0 \pm 0

Once the multiline TRL and OSLT calibration standards were defined, we used both sets of standards to calibrate the measurements of verification devices for comparison purposes. Figures 6-9 show calibrated S-parameters and

corresponding 95 % confidence bounds calculated from the sensitivity analysis performed in the NIST Uncertainty Framework for a 20 dB attenuator, a 40 dB attenuator, and a Beatty line. Additionally, the figures show results obtained with MultiCal™ [13], the original implementation of multiline TRL that does not provide uncertainty bounds. Dotted curves in the figures correspond to confidence bounds determined in the Uncertainty Framework.

In each of the figures, the measurements calibrated with both implementations of multiline TRL agree very well, while the OSLT-calibrated measurements and associated uncertainties are visibly noisier. For the 20 dB and 40 dB attenuators, the mean confidence intervals for $|S_{21}|$ are approximately ± 0.025 dB for multiline TRL and ± 0.022 dB for OSLT. For the Beatty line, the mean confidence intervals for $|S_{21}|$ are approximately ± 0.027 dB for multiline TRL and ± 0.097 dB for OSLT, while the mean upper confidence intervals for $|S_{11}|$ are +0.117 dB for multiline TRL and +0.547 dB for OSLT.

Fig. 1. Comparing the physical and polynomial models to the two TRL-calibrated measurements of the magnitudes of the 3.5 mm short standard's reflection coefficients.

Fig. 2. Comparing the physical and polynomial models to the two TRL-calibrated measurements of the phases of the 3.5 mm short standard's reflection coefficients.

Fig. 3. Comparing the physical and polynomial models to the two TRL-calibrated measurements of the magnitudes of the 3.5 mm open standard's reflection coefficients.

Fig. 4. Comparing the physical and polynomial models to the two TRL-calibrated measurements of the phases of the 3.5 mm open standard's reflection coefficients.

Fig. 5. Calibrated measurements of the magnitudes of the 3.5 mm load standard's reflection coefficients.

Fig. 6. Comparing measurements and 95% confidence intervals of the 20-dB attenuator's transmission coefficients with 3.5 mm multiline TRL and OSLT calibrations.

Fig. 7. Comparing measurements and 95% confidence intervals of the 40-dB attenuator's transmission coefficients with 3.5 mm multiline TRL and OSLT calibrations.

Fig. 8. Comparing measurements and 95% confidence intervals of the Beatty line's transmission coefficients with 3.5 mm multiline TRL and OSLT calibrations.

Fig. 9. Comparing measurements and 95% confidence intervals of the Beatty line's reflection coefficients with 3.5 mm multiline TRL and OSLT calibrations.

III. 2.4 MM COAXIAL CALIBRATIONS

For the 2.4 mm coaxial devices, we employed a similar strategy. Once again, we began by modeling the multiline TRL calibration standards, which consisted of a thru connection, an offset short, and three airlines of varying lengths. Table IV lists the line lengths and associated uncertainties for the multiline TRL standards, and Table V lists the other sources of uncertainty for the standards.

The NIST Microwave Uncertainty Framework was again employed to construct models for the calibration standards and propagate the uncertainties to the calibrated verification devices.

Next, the OSLT standards were modeled with the values and uncertainties listed in Tables V and VI. We compared our physical models of the offset open and short to the polynomial models specified by the manufacturer [12], as shown in Figures 10-13. Figures 10 and 12 plot the magnitudes of the reflection coefficients as a function of frequency, while Figures 11 and 13 plot the differences in phase with respect to those of the physical models. Additionally, we compared our physical models to measurements of the standards using the multiline TRL calibration, the results of which are also displayed in Figures 10-13. And similar to the 3.5 mm coaxial case, our physical models closely match the polynomial models, and the uncertainty bounds of our models, depicted by the dotted curves, span the majority of the measured values. This time, however, rather than modeling the load standard as a simple 50 Ohm resistor, we defined our load using the measured reflection coefficients from the multiline TRL calibration since the load was only specified to be 50 Ohms at frequencies less than 4 GHz. Figure 14 plots the magnitudes of the reflection coefficients. The values are clearly greater than -40 dB at most frequencies. Furthermore, we found it difficult to develop a simple physical model that accurately matched the measured results.

Table IV. Lengths and uncertainties of the 2.4 mm TRL standards.

Line Designation	Length (mm) \pm Uncertainty (Distribution)
Thru	0.000 \pm 0.005 (Rectangular)
AL15	14.996 \pm 0.005 (Rectangular)
AL17	17.496 \pm 0.005 (Rectangular)
AL30	29.992 \pm 0.005 (Rectangular)
Offset Shorts	0.000 \pm 0.005 (Rectangular)

Table V. Physical error mechanisms of the 2.4 mm standards.

Mechanism (units)	Value \pm Uncertainty (Distribution)
Inner Cond. Diameter (mm)	1.0423 \pm 0.004 (Rectangular)
Outer Cond. Diameter (mm)	2.4 \pm 0.005 (Rectangular)
Pin Diameter (mm)	0.511 \pm 0.005 (Rectangular)
Pin Depth (mm)	0.0065 \pm 0.0065 (Rectangular)
Metal Conductivity (S/m)	6 \times 10 ⁶ \pm 5 \times 10 ⁶ (Rectangular)
Relative Dielectric Constant	1 \pm 0
Dielectric Loss Tangent	0 \pm 0

Table VI. Physical error mechanisms of the 2.4 mm OSLT standards.

Mechanism (units)	Value \pm Uncertainty (Distribution)
Open Offset Length (mm)	6.75 \pm 0.02 (Rectangular)
Open Metal Conductivity (S/m)	5 \times 10 ⁶ \pm 4 \times 10 ⁶ (Rectangular)
Open Conductance (1/ Ω)	0 \pm 0
Open Capacitance (pF)	0 \pm 0
Short Offset Length (mm)	6.75 \pm 0.02 (Rectangular)
Short Metal Conductivity (S/m)	6 \times 10 ⁶ \pm 5 \times 10 ⁶ (Rectangular)
Short Resistance (Ω)	0 \pm 0
Short Inductance (nH)	0 \pm 0

Once the multiline TRL and OSLT calibration standards were defined, we used both calibrations to measure a set of verification devices for comparison purposes. Figures 15-19 show calibrated S-parameters and corresponding 95 % confidence bounds calculated in the NIST Uncertainty Framework for an offset short, a load, and an airline. Additionally, the figures show results using MultiCalTM.

Fig. 10. Comparing the physical and polynomial models to the three TRL-calibrated measurements of the magnitudes of the 2.4 mm short standard's reflection coefficients.

Fig. 13. Comparing the physical and polynomial models to the three TRL-calibrated measurements of the phases of the 2.4 mm open standard's reflection coefficients.

Fig. 11. Comparing the physical and polynomial models to the three TRL-calibrated measurements of the phases of the 2.4 mm short standard's reflection coefficients.

Fig. 14. Calibrated measurements of the magnitudes of the 2.4 mm load standard's reflection coefficients.

Fig. 12. Comparing the physical and polynomial models to the three TRL-calibrated measurements of the magnitudes of the 2.4 mm open standard's reflection coefficients.

In each of the figures, we compared the calibrated measurements using both implementations of multiline TRL and found that they agree very well. For the airline, the mean confidence intervals for $|S_{21}|$ are approximately ± 0.030 dB for multiline TRL and ± 0.015 dB for OSLT, and the mean confidence intervals for $\text{Arg}\{S_{21}\}$ are approximately $\pm 0.381^\circ$ for multiline TRL and $\pm 0.402^\circ$ for OSLT. For the load, the mean upper confidence intervals for $|S_{11}|$ are $+3.51$ dB for multiline TRL and $+3.82$ dB for OSLT. For the offset short, the mean confidence intervals for $|S_{11}|$ are approximately ± 0.050 dB for multiline TRL and ± 0.025 dB for OSLT, and the mean confidence intervals for $\text{Arg}\{S_{11}\}$ are approximately $\pm 0.521^\circ$ for multiline TRL and $\pm 1.790^\circ$ for OSLT.

Fig. 15. Comparing measurements and 95% confidence intervals of the magnitudes of the airline's transmission coefficients with 2.4 mm TRL and OSLT calibrations.

Fig. 18. Comparing measurements and 95% confidence intervals of the magnitudes of the short's reflection coefficients with 2.4 mm TRL and OSLT calibrations.

Fig. 16. Comparing measurements and 95% confidence intervals of the phases of the airline's transmission coefficients with 2.4 mm TRL and OSLT calibrations.

Fig. 19. Comparing measurements and 95% confidence intervals of the phases of the short's reflection coefficients with 2.4 mm TRL and OSLT calibrations.

Fig. 17. Comparing measurements and 95% confidence intervals of the load's reflection coefficients with 2.4 mm multiline TRL and OSLT calibrations.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

We have developed physical models of 2.4 mm and 3.5 mm coaxial calibration kits for vector network analyzers that support multiline TRL and OSLT calibrations within the NIST Microwave Uncertainty Framework. In both cases, the verification devices measured with the two calibration approaches agree to within their respective uncertainties. Although other sources of uncertainty may be included in a final uncertainty analysis, we believe these minor additions will not significantly affect the overall uncertainties.

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